

Perceived Stress and its Association with Hikikomori Traits: An Empirical Study among Adults in India

Saakshi Suvarna¹ and Vidya Bhat²

*Symbiosis Institute of Health Sciences, Symbiosis International (Deemed University), Pune, Maharashtra¹
Department of Psychology, MIT Art Design and Technology University, Rajbaug, Loni Kalbhor, Pune, Maharashtra²*

Stress plays a pivotal role in developing Hikikomori traits, which represents a severe form of social withdrawal commonly found in Japan. Hikikomori has significant health risks, affecting an individual's psychosocial functioning and quality of life. Latest studies on Hikikomori have reported an increase in the prevalence in countries other than Japan, necessitating further investigations. The present research aims to explore the relationship between Perceived Stress and Hikikomori traits in Indian adults. The cross-sectional study consisted of 158 participants, both genders, between 18-45 years. Participants submitted a demographic data sheet, a 25-item Hikikomori Questionnaire and Perceived Stress Scale-10. Statistical analysis was done using SPSS-30. A significant positive correlation was found between Perceived Stress and Hikikomori Traits ($r=0.51$; $p<0.001$). The domains of PSS-10: Perceived Helplessness ($r=0.37$, $p<0.001$) and Lack of Self-Efficacy ($r=0.29$, $p<0.001$) were significant predictors of Hikikomori. Perceived Helplessness was the most significant predictor of Hikikomori, followed by Lack of Self-Efficacy. The results indicate that Perceived Stress, especially the helplessness domain, plays a significant role in predicting Hikikomori traits. The research highlights the importance of addressing emotional states related to stress, especially helplessness. Prevention and therapeutic interventions to identify, assess and address Hikikomori symptoms in Indian adults need to be tailored.

Keywords: Hikikomori, stress, perceived stress, social withdrawal

Hikikomori represents a form of severe social isolation commonly seen in Japan. It is characterized by a withdrawal from social or work-related activities, often leading to extended periods of isolation from society (Figueiredo, 2023). Though there exists immense debate over a universally accepted definition of Hikikomori, it is often characterized by extreme social withdrawal experienced for a duration of six months or more (Figueiredo, 2023). The Japanese Ministry of Health and Labor in 2003 articulated an elaborate and specific criteria for Hikikomori. This included key characteristics such as a lifestyle predominantly and excessively centered around one's home, no interest/ willingness and reluctance to attend school, work or maintain personal relationships, that occur for at least six months, excluding cases attributed to schizophrenia, intellectual disability or any mental health disorder (Teo & Gaw, 2010). Nevertheless, it is not rare or uncommon to find Hikikomori being comorbid with other known psychiatric illness such as schizophrenia, depression and PTSD. Hence, the condition can be compartmentalized into Primary Hikikomori (where there is

no known association with a psychiatric condition) and Secondary Hikikomori (Hikikomori which is caused by a known & recognized psychiatric condition) for better clarity (Frankova, 2019).

While Hikikomori or social withdrawal is not a new occurrence, it has gained attention and become increasingly observed in recent years. There is now a growing need to understand the etiological and risk factors associated with the condition. Numerous risk factors such as internet use (Tateno et al., 2019; Solanki et al., 2023), parenting/attachment style (Sandhu & Sharma, 2015; Krieg & Dickie, 2011), psycho-behavioral traits (Bonnaire & Roignot, 2023; Katsuki et al., 2019), societal structures and settings (Furlong, 2008), age (Kanai et al., 2024) or, in certain instances, socio-economic conditions (Nonaka & Sakai, 2021; Umeda & Kawakami, 2012) have been investigated in relation to Hikikomori. The present research paper provides an understanding of a relatively underexplored topic of Perceived Stress and its relation to Hikikomori Traits.

Currently, the presence of Hikikomori is a substantial concern within the realm of healthcare, specifically in psychiatry. Existing literature on Hikikomori shows significant impairments for individuals with the condition; with decreased ability to function socially and adverse effects on individuals' mental health, education and workforce stability (Kato et al., 2019). Furthermore, studies done on Hikikomori indicate a 6.1 times higher risk of mood disorder in individuals who have previously experienced Hikikomori (Koyama et al., 2010). WHO also declared loneliness and social isolation as a global public health concern, comparing its mortality rates to other well-established risk factors such as smoking, obesity and physical inactivity (World Health Organisation, n.d.). This shows the adverse effects social isolation can have on individuals, but also concurrently demonstrates the detrimental effect of Hikikomori on individuals' health and mental health.

Author Note

¹Saakshi Suvarna, Symbiosis Institute of Health Sciences, Symbiosis International (Deemed University), Pune, Maharashtra

²Dr. Vidya Bhat, Associate Professor, School of Vedic Sciences
Department of Psychology, MIT Art Design and Technology
University, Rajbaug, Loni Kalbhor, Pune, Maharashtra
ORCID: 0000000206234831

We have no known conflict of interest to disclose.

Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to
Dr. Vidya Bhat, Associate Professor, School of Vedic Sciences
Department of Psychology, MIT Art Design and Technology
University, Rajbaug, Loni Kalbhor, Pune, Maharashtra
E-mail: vidya.bhat@gmail.com

Alarming, Hikikomori was previously thought to be a syndrome exclusively existing within the boundaries of Japan, but now we see an increasing prevalence of the condition in other countries. Research from countries like Spain (Malagón-Amor et al., 2018; Ovejero et al., 2013), Oman (Sakamoto et al., 2005), France (Chauliac et al., 2017), India, South Korea and the United States (Teo et al., 2014) have identified and shown the prevalence of Hikikomori in countries other than Japan. These findings are in line with Chauhan et al. (2021) who investigated Hikikomori in the Indian setting; notably, their results indicated that out of 102 participants, 51 individuals met the criteria for being at-risk for Hikikomori after the Covid-19 pandemic. Therefore, Hikikomori is no longer the culturally bound syndrome we once thought it to be, and there is a growing need to learn and understand this syndrome better.

Though studies have been conducted on Hikikomori outside Japan, significant gaps still remain that inhibit an adequate and comprehensive understanding of the condition in other countries. Research in India on the topic has also remained abysmally low, and in instances where researches have been conducted, the sample size remains far too low (typically less than 50 participants), raising questions about the generalizability of these findings. The increase and rising prevalence of the condition highlight the need to comprehend and assess various factors that can serve as etiological factors or risk factors associated with Hikikomori, paving the way to preventive care and services targeted at-risk individuals, preventing the condition from developing and becoming more debilitating in individuals.

Stress and more specifically perceived stress is one such area that could play an important role in the development of Hikikomori Traits, but also one that can easily be addressed in treatment. Perceived stress over one's life can easily exacerbate or give rise to Hikikomori symptoms, where individuals may withdraw from social life as a coping mechanism to handle the stress they are experiencing (Bonnaire & Roignot, 2023). Though there has not been any previous research directly correlating these two variables, several studies have explored similar elements. Nonaka and Sakai (2021) demonstrated a significant correlation between psychological stress and cases of Hikikomori, emphasizing how Hikikomori is often triggered by high-stress events. Shuster et al. (2023) assessed perceived stress and coping among university students during the COVID-19 pandemic and concluded that avoidance-related coping strategies (like social withdrawal) significantly predicted perceived stress. Similar results were found by Allen (2021) who investigated the use of coping strategies such as avoidance and its relation with perceived stress using computer-based avatar tasks. Results indicated a strong positive relation between resignation/withdrawal and perceived stress. Given that numerous studies have evidenced the potential for perceived stress in development vulnerability to Hikikomori, there exists no current research directly investigated how perceived stress can influence Hikikomori Trait vulnerability.

The present study hypothesized that perceived stress would directly correlate with Hikikomori vulnerability. The higher the perceived stress, the higher would be the scores for Hikikomori in the Indian adult population. Overall, the research aims to not only understand the relationship between Hikikomori and perceived stress, but also to add further to the research being done on the broader loneliness epidemic seen in the current generation.

Method

Participants

In this cross-sectional study, a total of 158 individuals of mixed genders, aged between 18-45 years, were recruited through random sampling. The sample was restricted to this age group, as previous studies have shown a higher prevalence of Hikikomori in individuals in their early 20s. However, the sample age was expanded to see age-related susceptibility to the condition and to explore age groups less represented in existing research.

Appropriate sample size was calculated using G*Power, based on an expected correlation effect size of 0.30, a significance level (α) of 0.05 and desired power of 0.90 for a two-tailed test. To account for an anticipated dropout rate of 20%, the initial sample size was increased to 136 participants. To further ensure sufficient power to detect a true effect, even with potential participant loss, the target sample size was set to 150 participants.

Individuals with inability to accurately respond or consent to the questionnaire were excluded from the study (cognitive impairments, physical or mental conditions, language barriers).

Measures

Perceived Stress Scale- 10 (PSS-10): PSS-10 developed by Cohen et al. (1983) is one of the most widely used instruments to measure Perceived Stress. It is a self-administered scale consisting of a series of questions probing on thoughts and feelings about stressors occurring during the past month. More specifically, it measures the degree to which events in one's life are appraised as stressful and how unpredictable, uncontrollable and overloaded people find their lives to be. Each item is rated on a four-point scale with scores ranging from 0-40, with higher scores reflecting greater Perceived Stress. The PSS-10 measures two domains relevant to the degree to which one experiences Perceived Stress: Perceived Helplessness and Lack of Self-efficacy. Studies have established the reliability and validity of the PSS in different countries and settings. The Cronbach alpha score for PSS-10 was > 0.70 , indicating strong internal consistency. For test-retest validity, PSS-10 has a correlation coefficient of > 0.70 , indicating strong positive correlations between results, signifying greater reliability (Lee, 2012).

The 25-item Hikikomori Questionnaire: The 25-item Hikikomori Questionnaire (HQ-25) developed by Teo et al. (2018) is a self-administered questionnaire measuring the severity and vulnerability of Hikikomori traits in individuals. HQ-25 measures three factors that are indicated risks for Hikikomori: Lack of Sociality, Isolation and Lack of Emotional Support. It assesses thoughts, feelings and behaviours associated with Hikikomori that occur within the previous 6 months of the test. Total score ranges between 0-100, with higher score representing more severe Hikikomori Trait vulnerability. A cutoff of 42 is indicative of severe risk of Hikikomori. Each item is answered on a 5-point scale ranging from 0 (strongly disagree) to 4 (agree strongly). Previous studies have indicated a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.98 for the questionnaire. Test-retest reliability scores showed a correlation coefficient of 0.95 ($p < 0.001$), indicating great reliability (Teo et al., 2018). Overall, HQ-25 achieves fairly good diagnostic accuracy and is the most frequently used and reliable tool to measure Hikikomori vulnerability.

Procedure

At the start of the study, participants were informed of the purpose and procedure of the research, any potential risk and benefits, along with their right to confidentiality, voluntary participation and withdrawal at any given time. Following consent, participants were then asked to fill a basic demographic sheet assessing age, gender, educational level and household monthly income. Participants then were administered two standardized assessment tools: The 25-item Hikikomori Questionnaire and the Perceived Stress Scale. Data for correlations between Hikikomori Traits and Perceived Stress was analyzed by calculating the scores for each of the questionnaires using the required criteria of the questionnaire. This research was conducted in compliance with ethical standards of the relevant institute and was approved by the Institute Research and Ethics committee.

Statistical Analysis

The data was analysed by SPSS-30 software. Data was checked for completeness and consistency and outlier data was removed from the sample. Descriptive statistics were calculated for demographic variables. Normality of data was checked. Pearson's correlation was performed to check the associations between independent and dependent variables. Multi Linear Regression Analysis was conducted to evaluate predictive influence of perceived stress and its domains.

Results

The participants' age was diverse, with a mean age of 28 ($SD=8.26$). The sample consisted of 59 males (38.1%) and 96 females (61.9%). Participants' education level ranged between undergraduate to postgraduate level education.

Mean of HQ-25 was 37.5 ($SD=18$), slightly lower than the hikikomori vulnerability cutoff score of 42 (as mentioned by the scale). The results in Table I shows that the mean PSS-10 score was 19.6 ($SD=7.1$), showing moderate levels of Perceived Stress in the participants.

Table III

Summary of Results of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis of Domains of PSS-10, Age, Gender, and Education Level with HQ-25 Score

Criterion Variable- Hikikomori Traits						
Predictors	r	B	SE	β	t	Sig.
Domain 1- PSS-10 (Perceived Helplessness)	0.37***	1.16	0.23	0.35	4.87	0.0
Domain 2- PSS-10 (Lack of Self-Efficacy)	0.29***	1.62	0.44	0.27	3.66	0.0

Note. $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

Multiple Linear Regression was run for the total score of PSS-10 and both the domains of the scale (Perceived Helplessness and Lack of Self-Efficacy) to analyze how the domains contribute to Hikikomori vulnerability. Table III shows that both the domains were significant predictors of Hikikomori trait vulnerability. Perceived helplessness was most significant at $r=0.37$ ($p < 0.001$) followed by lack of self-efficacy at $r=0.29$ ($p < 0.001$). Results showed that the total score of the Perceived Stress scale did not prove to be a significant predictor

Scores of the participants on HQ-25 ranged from 4 to 82, with 50% of participants' scores ranging between 23-49. Twenty five percent of the participants scored above 49, crossing the threshold for Hikikomori vulnerability. Scores for PSS-10 ranged from 0 to 39, with 50% of participants scoring between 15-24. There was no significant difference in means across gender on either Perceived stress or Hikikomori.

Table I

Descriptive Statistics (N= 155)

Variables	Mean	SD
Age	28.1	8.2
Hikikomori Traits	37.5	18.0
Perceived Stress	19.6	7.1

The results from Table II showed a highly significant positive correlation between the HQ-25 total score and PSS-10 total score, $r=0.51$ ($p < 0.001$), implying that when Perceived Stress increases, there tends to be a higher risk of developing Hikikomori.

Domain-wise correlations of PSS-10, both domain 1 (Perceived Helplessness) and domain 2 (Lack of Self-Efficacy) had a significant relation to Hikikomori. While the former domain showed a correlation coefficient of $r=0.45$ ($p < 0.001$), the latter showed $r=0.39$ ($p < 0.001$). Indicating that both perceived helplessness and lack of self-efficacy strongly and positively correlate with the social withdrawal seen in Hikikomori.

Table II

Correlation between Hikikomori Traits and PSS-10 (Subdomains)

Pearson's Correlation Coefficient	
Variables	Hikikomori Traits
Perceived Stress	0.51***
Domain 1- Perceived Helplessness	0.45 ***
Domain 2- Lack of Self-Efficacy	0.39 ***

Note. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

of Hikikomori; this might be because of its high collinearity with other variables, which were the domains of perceived stress. The results indicate that perceived stress, especially perceived helplessness, might play a significant role in developing vulnerability of Hikikomori.

Discussion

This research aimed to explore the relationship between Hikikomori

and perceived stress in individuals from India. Mean score for Hikikomori in the present study was 37, indicating that participants had scores just below the required cutoff of 42 for Hikikomori vulnerability. Though these scores indicate a moderate susceptibility to the condition and warrant attention to prevent further exacerbation, they do fall below that reported in countries such as Japan ($M = 41.29$) (Teo et al., 2018) and South Korea ($M = 65.9$) (Choi et al., 2022). Interestingly, one may assume that the collectivist societal structure in countries such as India or Japan, where there is increased focus on maintaining familial and social relationships, may play a protective role in Hikikomori vulnerability. In countries with cohesive family systems and immense focus on the maintenance of interpersonal relationships, individuals may grow up developing more applicable real-world social skills. However, this assumption may no longer hold true. With rapidly changing societal structures in India and other collectivistic communities and a possible move to more nuclear, individualistic models, we may experience increasing prevalence and vulnerability to Hikikomori due to lower community support and increased expectations/pressure on individuals. This may explain why there is not a noticeable gap in the prevalence of the condition in countries such as Japan and India, which run on a more socialistic ethos and countries like the United States, where individuals view society in a more individualistic sense.

The study results indicate a high correlation between perceived stress and Hikikomori, confirming our initial hypothesis of a significant correlation between the two variables. As there were no previous studies directly correlating these variables, we based our hypothesis on the assumption that factors linked to Hikikomori, such as societal pressure and coercive parenting, can often contribute to a pattern of thinking characterized by lack of control, helplessness and a belief in the inadequacy to do work independently. These thinking patterns are all key elements of perceived stress. Though factors like societal pressure, coercive parenting, and socioeconomic conditions are more complex to address and often require collective long-term effort, the feeling of perceived stress is one that various psychotherapeutic approaches can address.

The population from the age group 26 to 30 years scored highest on Hikikomori traits, which exceeded or met the required threshold for indicated risk for Hikikomori. This coincides with existing literature, such as Koyama et al. (2010) and Yong and Nomura (2019) which reported Hikikomori onset being prevalent in young adulthood. Tailored intervention techniques targeted at minimizing stress experienced in this group can also help in the prevention and mitigation of the risk associated with the condition before the symptoms become more severe and debilitating.

In the present study, the regression analysis showed that while domains related to perceived stress like perceived helplessness and lack of self-efficacy significantly predicted scores for Hikikomori Trait, total perceived stress scores did not. Indicating that while there is a significant relationship between Hikikomori trait and perceived stress, it is the feeling of perceived helplessness and lack of self-efficacy that greatly predicts an individual's vulnerability to the condition. This result aligns with existing literature such as Yong and Kaneko (2016) which through qualitative interviews with individuals with Hikikomori emphasized that it was feelings of helplessness, powerlessness and hopelessness that often led to the social withdrawal seen in Hikikomori. Furthermore, while lack of self-efficacy has not been directly studied with social withdrawal in

adults, Watson and Nesdale (2012) presented findings that implied how low levels of social Self-Efficacy can contribute to rejection sensitivity, which in turn may lead to social withdrawal.

The present study not only fills a gap in literature but also adds to research conducted in the field. While researches like Nonaka and Sakai (2021) and Shuster et al. (2023) attempted to establish a relationship between Perceived Stress and social withdrawal, this study directly examines the correlation between these variables, providing a broader and clearer insight into the phenomenon. There are many potential areas for further research on this topic. Firstly, there is a need for longitudinal research in this area to understand the relationship between these variables further. Longitudinal research will help provide a better understanding of the phenomenon in relation to perceived stress and address this question more definitively. Secondly, more studies are needed to investigate the prevalence of Hikikomori in the older age groups. The present study investigated Hikikomori in the age group of 18-45 in India, as younger age groups have shown to have increased vulnerability to Hikikomori, and there has been limited researches done in India. Lastly, there is a need for studies investigating different aspects of cognition associated with Hikikomori, such as self-compassion and psychological inflexibility. Behavioral factors or life experiences are currently the focus of Hikikomori research; however, investigating cognitive aspects can give us valuable insights into thought patterns and mental processes and help in addressing root causes rather than the surface presentations of symptoms. On the whole, future research is needed to understand cognitive domains, social traits associated with Hikikomori, especially in the Indian context.

Implications of the Study

There are significant implications to this study, both for clinical and academic purposes. The research findings help understand the relationship between Perceived Stress and Hikikomori and the insight gives direction to how intervention aimed at preventing the rise of or reducing symptoms of Hikikomori could be formulated. Interventions like stress management programs and psychoeducation on coping strategies could be great preventive approaches to Hikikomori especially in younger adults. On the other hand, interventions for reducing severity of Hikikomori such as cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) can factor in the Perceived Stress by addressing individuals' subjective perception of stressor and restructuring such maladaptive thought patterns. Mental Health professionals and Psychiatrists would play a pivotal role in this domain.

Limitations of the Study

There are a few limitations to the current study, mainly the smaller sample size which can be widened through a major research project across state level. However, due to the study's novelty and the abysmally low research done on Hikikomori and Perceived Stress, the study tries to bridge the gaps in existing literature and provides invaluable understanding for the condition.

Conclusion

Hikikomori poses considerable health risks and significantly affects an individual's psycho-social functioning and is yet to be fully understood. This gap in comprehension of the phenomenon undoubtedly represents a significant challenge in the field of

healthcare and psychiatry. Finding the relationship between Hikikomori and Perceived Stress allowed us to explore important factors that increase susceptibility and vulnerability to the condition that is often vital to understand interventions that may help alleviate symptoms of Hikikomori. Overall, the study helped answer some vital questions that helped inform interventions but also built our understanding regarding the phenomenon at hand.

References

- Allen, M. T. (2021). Explorations of avoidance and approach coping and perceived stress with a computer-based avatar task: detrimental effects of resignation and withdrawal. *PeerJ*, 9(1), e11265. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.11265>
- Bonnaire, C., & Roignot, Z. (2023). Relationship between social withdrawal (hikikomori), personality, and coping in an adult population. *Psychiatry Investigation*, 20(8), 740-749. <https://doi.org/10.30773/pi.2023.0099>
- Chauhan, P. S., Singh, V., & Kumar, N. (2021). Severe social withdrawal and lockdown: a descriptive study of hikikomori in Indian youth. *International Journal of Management and Applied Science (IJMAS)*, 7(10), 22-27. https://ijmas.iraj.in/paper_detail.php?paper_id=18228&name=Severe_Social_Withdrawal_and_Lockdown:_A_Descriptive_Study_of_Hikikomori_in_Indian_Youth
- Chauliac, N., Couillet, A., Faivre, S., Brochard, N., & Terra, J.L. (2017). Characteristics of socially withdrawn youth in France: A retrospective study. *International Journal of Social Psychiatry*, 63(4), 339-344. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0020764017704474>
- Choi, T. Y., Lee, H. J., Je, S. R., & Kim, J. W. (2022). 1.3 Factors associated with Korean adolescent hikikomori: Loneliness, education level, and internet addiction. *Journal of the American Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry*, 61(10), S141-S142. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaac.2022.09.019>
- Cohen, S., Kamarck, T., & Mermelstein, R. (1983). A global measure of perceived stress. *Journal of Health and Social Behavior*, 24(4), 385-396. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2136404>
- Frankova, I. (2019). Similar but different: Psychological and Psychopathological Features of Primary and Secondary Hikikomori. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2019.00558>
- Furlong, A. (2008). The Japanese hikikomori phenomenon: Acute social withdrawal among young people. *The Sociological Review*, 56(2), 309-325. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-954x.2008.00790.x>
- Inês Mateus Figueiredo. (2023). Hikikomori syndrome: A cultural phenomenon not only limited to Japan. *International Journal of Social Psychiatry*, 70, 3. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00207640231210113>
- Kanai, K., Kitamura, Y., Zha, L., Tanaka, K., Ikeda, M., & Tomotaka Sobue. (2024). Prevalence of and factors influencing Hikikomori in Osaka City, Japan: A population-based cross-sectional study. *International Journal of Social Psychiatry*, 70(5), 967-980. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00207640241245926>
- Kato, T. A., Kanba, S., & Teo, A. R. (2019). Hikikomori: Multidimensional understanding, assessment and future international perspectives. *Psychiatry and Clinical Neurosciences*, 73(8), 427-440. <https://doi.org/10.1111/pcn.12895>
- Katsuki, R., Inoue, A., Indias, S., Kurahara, K., Kuwano, N., Funatsu, F., Kubo, H., Kanba, S., & Kato, T. A. (2019). Clarifying deeper psychological characteristics of hikikomori using the rorschach comprehensive system: A pilot case-control study. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2019.00412>
- Koyama, A., Miyake, Y., Kawakami, N., Tsuchiya, M., Tachimori, H., & Takeshima, T. (2010). Lifetime prevalence, psychiatric comorbidity and demographic correlates of "hikikomori" in a community population in Japan. *Psychiatry Research*, 176(1), 69-74. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2008.10.019>
- Krieg, A., & Dickie, J. R. (2011). Attachment and Hikikomori: A psychosocial developmental model. *International Journal of Social Psychiatry*, 59(1), 61-72. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0020764011423182>
- Malagón-Amor, Á., Martín-López, L. M., Córcoles, D., González, A., Bellsolà, M., Teo, A. R., Pérez, V., Bulbena, A., & Bergé, D. (2018). A 12-month study of the hikikomori syndrome of social withdrawal: Clinical characterisation and different subtypes proposal. *Psychiatry Research*, 270, 1039-1046. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2018.03.060>
- Nonaka, S., & Sakai, M. (2021a). A correlational study of socio-economic factors and the prevalence of Hikikomori in Japan from 2010 to 2019. *Comprehensive Psychiatry*, 108, 152-251. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.comppsy.2021.152251>
- Nonaka, S., & Sakai, M. (2021b). Psychological factors associated with social withdrawal (hikikomori). *Psychiatry Investigation*, 18(5), 463-470. <https://doi.org/10.30773/pi.2021.0050>
- Ovejero, S., Caro-Cañizares, I., de León-Martínez, V., & Baca-García, E. (2013). Prolonged social withdrawal disorder: A hikikomori case in Spain. *International Journal of Social Psychiatry*, 60(6), 562-565. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0020764013504560>
- Sakamoto, N., Martin, R. G., Kumano, H., Kuboki, T., & Al-Adawi, S. (2005). Hikikomori, is it a culture-reactive or culture-bound syndrome? Nidotherapy and a clinical vignette from Oman. *The International Journal of Psychiatry in Medicine*, 35(2), 191-198. <https://doi.org/10.2190/7weq-216d-tnvh-pqj1>
- Sandhu, G. K., & Sharma, V. (2015). Social withdrawal and social anxiety in relation to stylistic parenting dimensions in the Indian cultural context. *Research in Psychology and Behavioral Sciences*, 3(3), 51-59. <https://doi.org/10.12691/rpbs-3-3-2>
- Shuster, C. L., Tate, M. C., Schulz, C. T., Reyes, C. T., Drohan, M. M., Astorini, A. G., Stamates, A. L., Yang, M., & Robbins, M. L. (2023). Perceived stress and coping among university students amidst COVID-19 pandemic. *COVID*, 3(10), 1544-1553. <https://doi.org/10.3390/covid3100105>
- Tateno, M., Teo, A. R., Ukai, W., Kanazawa, J., Katsuki, R., Kubo, H., & Kato, T. A. (2019). Internet addiction, smartphone addiction, and hikikomori trait in Japanese young adult: Social isolation and social network. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2019.00455>
- Teo, A. R., Chen, J. I., Kubo, H., Katsuki, R., Sato-Kasai, M., Shimokawa, N., Hayakawa, K., Umene-Nakano, W., Aikens, J. E., Kanba, S., & Kato, T. A. (2018). Development and validation of the 25-item Hikikomori Questionnaire (HQ-25). *Psychiatry and Clinical Neurosciences*, 72(10), 780-788. <https://doi.org/10.1111/pcn.12691>
- Teo, A. R., Fetters, M. D., Stufflebam, K., Tateno, M., Balhara, Y., Choi, T. Y., Kanba, S., Mathews, C. A., & Kato, T. A. (2014). Identification of the hikikomori syndrome of social withdrawal: Psychosocial features and treatment preferences in four countries. *International Journal of Social Psychiatry*, 61(1), 64-72. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0020764014535758>
- Teo, A. R., & Gaw, A. C. (2010). Hikikomori, a Japanese culture-bound syndrome of social withdrawal? *The Journal of Nervous and Mental Disease*, 198(6), 444-449. <https://doi.org/10.1097/nmd.0b013e3181e086b1>
- Umeda, M., & Kawakami, N. (2012). Association of childhood family environments with the risk of social withdrawal ("hikikomori") in the community population in Japan. *Psychiatry and Clinical Neurosciences*, 66(2), 121-129. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1440-1819.2011.02292.x>
- World Health Organization (n.d.). *Social Isolation and Loneliness*. World Health Organization. <https://www.who.int/teams/social-determinants-of-health/demographic-change-and-healthy-ageing/social-isolation-and-loneliness>
- World Health Organization (2023, February 21). *Stress*. World Health Organization. <https://www.who.int/news-room/questions-and-answers/item/stress>
- Yong, R. K. F., & Kaneko, Y. (2016). Hikikomori, a phenomenon of social withdrawal and isolation in young adults marked by an anomic response to coping difficulties: A qualitative study exploring individual experiences from first- and second-person perspectives. *Open Journal of Preventive Medicine*, 06(01), 120. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ojpm.2016.61001>
- Yong, R., & Nomura, K. (2019). Hikikomori is most associated with interpersonal relationships, followed by suicide risks: A secondary analysis of a national cross-sectional study. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2019.00247>

Received August 13, 2025

Revision received August 25, 2025

Accepted August 28, 2025